

Analysis of Passenger Complaints with ARTIW Methods in the Dimension of Global Airline Alliances*

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Airline industry Airline management Airline alliances Passenger complaints ARTIW</p> <hr/> <p>Received: 4 May 2025 Revised: 14 July 2025 Accepted: 30 July 2025</p>	<p>Passenger complaints provide airlines with valuable information for assessing service quality and customer satisfaction. They enable airlines to understand customer expectations, identify deficiencies in their service processes and develop improvement strategies, thereby playing an important role in securing a long-term competitive advantage. This study examines complaints directed at airlines within global airline alliances (Star Alliance, Oneworld and SkyTeam) to highlight areas where passenger satisfaction could be improved. It utilizes monthly reports from the U.S. Department of Transportation's Office of Aviation Consumer Protection, spanning the years 2018–2023, which examine passenger complaints directed at foreign airlines operating flights to the United States. The report categorizes passenger complaints into the following 12 areas: flight problems, oversales, reservations - ticketing and boarding; fares, refunds, baggage, customer service, disability, advertising, discrimination, animals and other complaints. Among complaints directed at Star Alliance and Oneworld airline alliances, the study found that refunds, baggage and reservations, ticketing and boarding complaints ranked in the top three. Among complaints directed at SkyTeam airline alliances, the top three were refunds, baggage and flight problems.</p>

1. Introduction

Airline companies continue to operate in an increasingly competitive environment characterised by rapid change and structural transformation. In this context, they are making various efforts to differentiate themselves from their competitors and win passengers' custom (Seo et al., 2020: 13). Efforts to prioritise passenger satisfaction by improving service quality are at the forefront of these activities. While airlines' ultimate goal is to ensure passenger satisfaction, this is not always achievable. Ultimately, it is likely that they will receive complaints from passengers. Airlines that are unable to develop an effective complaint management process may experience problems escalating, which could lead to the airline being associated with these problems (Atalık, 2007: 417). In the past, passengers could only share complaints with their immediate circle, but today, thanks to communication technology, they can publicize their complaints to a

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much wider audience, and people with similar experiences can connect regardless of distance (Ward and Ostrom, 2006: 228). These complaints can damage companies' reputations and cause other passengers to choose different airlines (Sparks and Browning, 2010: 799). This, in turn, leads to airlines placing great importance on managing passenger complaints effectively.

Airline companies are increasingly forming strategic alliances in order to take full advantage of the economies of scale offered by internationalisation (Rajasekar and Fouts, 2009: 95). These alliances involve cooperative arrangements between two or more carriers, including joint operations, with the aim of increasing competitive strength and, consequently, overall performance (Morrish and Hamilton, 2002: 402). These alliances primarily aim to increase national and international flight frequencies, expand bilateral airline agreements, leverage low-cost advantages and gain a competitive edge over rivals (Karakavuz, 2017). Code-sharing agreements play an important role in strategic alliances by facilitating access to different markets and offering passengers a seamless travel experience with a single ticket for connecting flights (Gerede, 2002: 150). However, inconsistent services offered by alliance members may lead to negative outcomes, such as a decrease in brand loyalty, particularly from the perspective of the airline from which the ticket was purchased. This study will examine passenger complaints about airlines belonging to the Star Alliance, Oneworld and SkyTeam airline alliances, and highlight areas where airline alliances need to improve passenger satisfaction. The research question of the study is as follows:

RQ1: How do passenger dissatisfactions vary according to airline alliances?

RQ2: What are the relative importance levels of the sources of passenger complaints in terms of airline alliances?

Increasing competition in air transport has necessitated not only competition focused on service quality, but also strategic alliances. Against this backdrop, the question arises as to how global airline alliances affect the passenger experience while ensuring operational efficiency. The aim of this study is to conduct a comparative analysis of the structure of passenger complaints according to global airline alliances, and to identify opportunities for improvement in passenger satisfaction for alliance members, within the framework of the formulated research questions.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1. Airline Passenger Complaints

Almost every business may encounter consumer complaints at some point. Strategically managing such situations can be difficult because the reasons for the complaints may not be clear (Goodwin and Ross, 1990: 40). Einwiller and Steilen (2015: 196) define a consumer complaint as 'an expression of dissatisfaction aimed at drawing attention to perceived abuse by an organisation and achieving personal or collective goals'. Businesses now recognise that relationships with consumers must be long-term, and that complaint management is of great importance (Bell and Luddington, 2006: 221).

Airlines' ability to sustain their assets depends on retaining existing customers and acquiring new ones. In doing so, it is particularly important to prioritise the relationship with existing customers. From a business perspective, the cost of acquiring new customers is higher than that of retaining existing ones (Shea et al., 2004: 105; Aldırmaz-Akkaya & Ünal, 2019: 1708). Furthermore, fostering successful relationships with existing customers can transform them into voluntary brand ambassadors who promote the airline. At the same time, complaints from passengers will help airlines to understand their customers' perspectives, enabling them to develop business strategies that focus on passengers (Tyrrell and Woods, 2004: 183). In a sense, complaints offer airlines valuable strategic insights into their ability to ensure passenger satisfaction and their actual success (Sarı and Onat, 2013: 561).

For airlines to be successful, it is important that they have access to systematic market information that they can evaluate. However, obtaining this information can be difficult and costly, particularly for those operating in multiple markets. In this regard, consumer complaints can provide airlines with unique insights (Bai et al.,

2022: 13). When addressing complaints, companies should first identify their characteristics and develop strategies accordingly (Ye and Tripathi, 2016: 3844). The ease of complaining via the internet and the emergence of numerous platforms has increased the number of complaints, especially today. Nevertheless, the richness of consumer complaints provides businesses with the opportunity to access a wide range of information, if they can evaluate it (Yilmaz et al., 2016: 946). For a business aiming to be consumer-focused, complaints provide access to a wide range of first-hand, uninterpreted and unaltered information about the services it provides (Plymire, 1991: 43). In this sense, airlines must recognise that each passenger's complaints and expectations are unique when developing their complaint management strategies (Olatunde et al., 2020: 89). This may be due to consumers' psychological, cultural, religious and other characteristics, as well as special circumstances. For instance, Major and Hubbard (2019: 52) found in their US-based study that complaints from passengers with disabilities have increased over time, and that these complaints differ between airlines. In this context, the study reveals that some airlines are guilty of consistently disregarding effective service provision for individuals with disabilities. Mattila and Mount (2003: 142) also state that consumers' propensity towards technology is an important factor in complaint management. The same study emphasises that consumers who use technology extensively are more satisfied when their complaints are responded to quickly.

Consumers are generally eager to share their negative experiences of service failures with others. This is a negative situation for businesses. Therefore, to prevent complaints being communicated to others and to demonstrate successful complaint management, airlines must ensure that complaints are directed to the company itself (Balaji et al., 2015: 647). With the development of internet technology, negative experiences are now shared with a much larger audience, and potential customers can easily access this information (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004: 39). The widespread use of social media around the world today has made these platforms very important for communicating passenger complaints. The traditional structure of complaint submission and dissemination has been dismantled. This has transformed complaints that could previously only be shared within the complainant's immediate circle or made public with limited resources, into a structure accessible to anyone with an internet connection (Einwiller & Steilen, 2015: 196). Hassan et al. (2020: 58) state that consumers search for information online when choosing an airline, and that this information influences their choice. This may prevent airlines from achieving the desired results from their advertising campaigns, which require substantial funding. Sa'ait et al. (2016: 74) state that consumers consider information from other consumers who have had positive or negative experiences with a service to be much more valuable than company advertisements. Olatunde et al. (2020: 89) emphasise that negative reviews from airline consumers can result in financial losses for companies. Therefore, airline companies must address and manage consumer complaints strategically.

Competitive dynamics in the air transport sector can cause companies to adopt cost-focused strategies, which can lead to issues relating to service quality. In this context, low-cost airlines have reduced their costs and entered the market with low-priced tickets by offering a simplified product and providing services at secondary airports outside major city centres (Pels et al., 2009: 335). It could be argued that this development has impacted the diversification of consumer complaints. This is because other airlines may also reduce the quality of their services in order to compete with the low-cost business model. In the airline industry, customer service activities are becoming increasingly important alongside rising costs, intense competition and structural changes (Major and Hubbard, 2019: 43).

Businesses should not downplay problems that arise or complaints from consumers, and their offerings should align with their promises (Benoit, 1997: 184). Problems experienced by consumers with a purchased service influence their overall evaluation of it (Kim and Lehto, 2012: 466). In the complaint management process, the response that an airline company gives to the complainant is the final outcome of the interaction (Davidow, 2003: 247). It also provides important information about the value that airlines place on their customers (Cho et al., 2002: 2308). In conclusion, the way airlines manage complaints and respond to passenger complaints determines how passengers behave after making a complaint (Davidow, 2003: 225). However, it is also important for airlines to successfully manage their complaints process and announce the results using various communication tools, so the public can learn about their success (Harrison-Walker,

2001: 407). This will positively influence both existing and potential future customers. It should not be forgotten that employees who interact with customers play a key role in how companies manage consumer complaints effectively (Karatepe, 2006: 87). Airline companies must manage their human resources strategically throughout this process.

Although different European countries have different approaches to dealing with airline passenger complaints, it is not possible to say that every country is successful in this regard. At the European level, common regulations enacted by the European Union have ensured a shared approach to this issue. In the United Kingdom, for example, the Civil Aviation Authority (CAA) manages approximately 20,000 complaints about airlines or airports submitted by consumers each year (Creutzfeldt and Berlin, 2016: 148). The deregulation of the airline industry in the United States in 1978 eliminated government control over airline companies in some areas. However, the federal government continues to regulate certain practices aimed at protecting airline customers, in addition to its supervisory role in aviation safety (Tang, 2016: 1). In Turkey, the Passenger Rights Coordination Office, which is part of the General Directorate of Civil Aviation, is responsible for evaluating passenger complaints (Çelebi, 2015: 95). However, it cannot be said that there is an effective public complaint management process in Turkey. Despite these developments, an absence of a comprehensive approach to consumer complaints is evident in almost every country.

2.2. Global Airline Alliances

Airline alliances are defined as structures in which two or more airlines cooperate commercially and integrate their marketing and operational activities to a certain extent (Doganis, 2009). The three most well-known alliances today are Star Alliance, Oneworld and SkyTeam. Star Alliance has the most extensive global network. Oneworld is particularly popular for business travel. SkyTeam has a stronger presence in the European and Asian markets. While the primary goal of alliances is to expand their global networks, their impact on the customer experience remains a subject of debate. The impact of airline alliances on the passenger experience is evaluated in terms of positive and negative aspects. Advantages include code sharing between alliance member airlines, ease of ticketing for connecting flights, joint loyalty programmes and access to airport lounges, all of which aim to offer passengers a more integrated and comfortable travel experience. However, inconsistent service quality can result from the lack of full coordination of service standards among all alliance member airlines, particularly on connecting flights. Additionally, issues at one airline can affect other member companies within the alliance structure, complicating complaint management. While alliances are expected to develop a common approach to passenger satisfaction, achieving this unity is difficult given that each airline operates according to its own national legislation, operational structure and cultural differences. Therefore, alongside the advantages of a global network, improving the passenger experience sustainably emerges as an important managerial and strategic challenge for airline alliances (Gudmundsson & Lechner, 2006; Tiernan et al., 2008).

3. Methodology

The Air Travel Consumer Report is a monthly publication by the Office of Aviation Consumer Protection, which forms part of the US Department of Transportation. The report is compiled from statistical data provided by various departments within the Office and the wider Department. The Office of Aviation Consumer Protection fulfils its duties by collecting and responding to consumer complaints relating to air travel and by publishing information on aviation complaints in the United States. Through its work, the Office aims to assist, educate and protect aviation consumers. The Office is also responsible for ensuring that the U.S. Department of Transportation's monthly Air Travel Consumer Report and the Department's website contain clear and useful information about the rights of air travellers (DOT, 2023). In this context, this study used the Air Travel Consumer Reports published by the US Department of Transportation's Aviation Consumer Protection Office as a dataset covering the period from 2018 to 2023.

The study used Average Rank Transformation into Weight (ARTIW) as a multi-criteria decision-making method to calculate criterion weights based on expert evaluations. ARTIW is a method used to determine criterion weights in multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) problems. First introduced in 2011, it involves ranking the criteria and then converting these rankings into weights for use in the decision-making process. In this method, experts determine the importance levels (weights) of the criteria that define the quality of an element, and these are then normalised so that their totals equal one. The equation used for this calculation is provided below (Sivilevičius, 2011).

$$\omega_j = \frac{(m+1) - \bar{R}_j}{\sum_{j=1}^m \bar{R}_j}$$

This method provides a practical solution, particularly for complex, multidimensional decision-making problems, as it establishes the importance of criteria based on their ranking. In customer-focused sectors such as aviation, the ARTIW method is useful for evaluating performance indicators such as passenger complaints and for creating decision support systems. The criteria and codes used in this study, conducted using the ARTIW method, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Criteria, Definitions, and Codes Used in the Study

Code	Criteria	Definitions
C1	Flight Problems	Cancellations, delays, or any other deviations from schedule, whether planned or unplanned.
C2		All bumping problems, whether or not the airline complied with DOT oversales regulations.
C3	Reservations, Ticketing, Boarding	Airline or travel agent mistakes made in reservations and ticketing; problems in making reservations and obtaining tickets due to busy telephone lines or waiting in line, or delays in mailing tickets; problems boarding the aircraft (except oversales).
C4		Incorrect or incomplete information about fares, discount fare conditions and availability, overcharges, fare increases and level of fares in general.
C5	Refunds	Problems in obtaining refunds for unused or lost tickets, fare adjustments, or bankruptcies.
C6	Baggage	Claims for lost, damaged or delayed baggage, charges for excess baggage, carry-on problems, and difficulties with airline claims procedures.
C7		Rude or unhelpful employees, inadequate meals or cabin service, treatment of delayed passengers, unsatisfactory seat assignment (non-disability), problems with family seating.
C8	Disability	Civil rights complaints by air travelers with disabilities.
C9	Advertising	Advertising that is unfair, misleading or offensive to consumers.
C10	Discrimination	Civil rights complaints by air travelers (other than disability); for example, complaints based on race, national origin, religion, etc.
C11		Animals
C12	Other	Frequent flyer, smoking, tours credit, cargo problems, security, airport facilities, claims for bodily injury, and others not classified above.

4. Results and Discussion

This section first presents the number of complaints by strategic alliance and complaint category. It then provides the relative importance rankings of the relevant complaint categories (criteria), which are based on expert opinions. In this context, passenger complaints submitted to the US Department of Transportation between 2018 and 2023 were analysed first for the three major airline alliances. Complaints relating to the

Star Alliance, oneworld and SkyTeam airline alliances were evaluated under 12 main categories, with both the number of complaints and their proportion of the total being compared. Table 2 shows the complaint categories and numbers by airline alliance.

Table 2: Number of Complaints by Alliance

Alliance	Skyteam		Oneworld		Star Alliance	
	Number of Complaints	Percentage (%)	Number of Complaints	Percentage (%)	Number of Complaints	Percentage (%)
Flight Problems	2087	7,76	1902	7,19	5547	6,46
Oversales	256	0,95	243	0,92	618	0,72
Reservations, Ticketing, Boarding	2025	7,53	2550	9,64	6259	7,29
Fares	1360	5,06	1672	6,32	3838	4,47
Refunds	15210	56,55	14583	55,12	57690	67,19
Baggage	4784	17,79	3950	14,93	8990	10,47
Customer Service	597	2,22	661	2,50	1649	1,92
Disability	323	1,20	349	1,32	695	0,81
Advertising	24	0,09	37	0,14	43	0,05
Discrimination	32	0,12	71	0,27	137	0,16
Animals	3	0,01	0	0,00	9	0,01
Other	196	0,73	439	1,65	386	0,45
Total	26897	100	26457	100	85861	100

According to Table 2, Star Alliance stands out in terms of the total number of complaints received. With 85,861 complaints, it received significantly more than both Oneworld (26,457) and SkyTeam (26,897). This is believed to be primarily due to Star Alliance having more member airlines and a broader flight network.

Examining complaint categories in detail reveals that the 'refunds' category accounts for the highest number of complaints in all alliances. 67.19% of Star Alliance complaints, 55.12% of Oneworld complaints and 56.55% of Skyteam complaints are related to refunds. Star Alliance's particularly high percentage shows that passengers experience more problems with this alliance when cancelling their tickets. This finding suggests that the transparency and speed of refund processes directly impact passenger satisfaction within each alliance. Baggage complaints are a more significant problem for passengers of the Skyteam alliance. While 17.79% of SkyTeam complaints are baggage-related, this figure is 14.93% for oneworld and 10.47% for Star Alliance. This suggests that SkyTeam member airlines are less effective at addressing issues such as baggage transfer, loss or damage.

Examining complaints relating to reservations, ticketing and boarding processes reveals that passengers of the Oneworld alliance experience greater dissatisfaction. While 9.64% of Oneworld complaints fall into this category, the figure is 7.53% for Skyteam and 7.29% for Star Alliance. This suggests that airlines affiliated with the oneworld alliance need to improve their ticketing systems, online reservation processes and airport check-in services. Flight issues are also a notable topic. SkyTeam passengers complained about flight-related issues at a rate of 7.76%, compared to 7.19% for oneworld passengers and 6.46% for Star Alliance passengers. Flight cancellations, delays and rescheduling appear to be more problematic for Skyteam in particular.

In the 'fares' category, Oneworld received the highest number of complaints at 6.32%, followed by Skyteam at 5.06% and Star Alliance at 4.47%. The complexity of pricing policies and additional fees, as well as last-minute changes, may have caused greater dissatisfaction among Oneworld passengers. Alliances reported low rates in other complaint categories, such as customer service, disability services, advertising, discrimination, and animal transport. However, SkyTeam reported a higher customer service rate of 2.22%, while Oneworld reported 2.50% and Star Alliance 1.92%. Regarding complaints relating to disabled passengers specifically, SkyTeam reported a rate of 1.20%, Oneworld 1.32%, and Star Alliance 0.81%. These figures suggest that SkyTeam and Oneworld airlines have more issues with customer service and accessibility.

The number of complaints recorded in the categories of advertising, discrimination and animal transport was generally low. However, Star Alliance had a relatively high rate of discrimination complaints at 0.16%, while complaints relating to animals were negligible across all alliances.

According to the ARTiW method employed in the study, the ranking of criteria as determined by experts offers valuable insights into the critical areas of passenger complaints. Expert evaluations have revealed the quantitative and qualitative importance of passenger complaints. Table 3 presents the findings regarding the importance levels of the criteria in this context.

Table 3: Importance levels of criteria

Criteria	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	
E1	1	4	3	5	6	2	7	10	9	8	11	12	
E2	1	5	6	7	2	3	4	8	10	9	11	12	
E3	1	5	6	2	8	3	4	10	7	9	11	12	
E4	2	7	6	1	5	8	3	9	10	4	11	12	
E5	4	5	3	1	2	6	8	11	10	9	7	12	
E6	6	3	5	9	10	7	2	4	8	1	11	12	
E7	2	6	4	1	7	5	3	8	11	9	10	12	
E8	1	6	7	2	5	4	3	8	10	11	9	12	
E9	2	3	7	5	6	4	10	8	11	1	12	9	
E10	1	6	2	7	5	4	3	8	11	9	10	12	
Eq.1 $R_j = \sum_{i=1}^n R_{ij}$	21	50	49	40	56	46	47	84	97	70	103	117	
Eq.3 $\bar{R}_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n R_{ij}}{n}$	2,1	5	4,9	4	5,6	4,6	4,7	8,4	9,7	7	10,3	11,7	T
Eq.9 $\omega_j = \frac{(m+1) - \bar{R}_j}{\sum_{j=1}^m \bar{R}_j}$	0,140	0,103	0,104	0,115	0,095	0,108	0,106	0,059	0,042	0,077	0,035	0,017	1,00
Priority	1	6	5	2	7	3	4	9	10	8	11	12	

According to the obtained ranking, the complaint category with the highest priority was 'Flight Problems'. Experts have confirmed that flight cancellations, delays and scheduling disruptions directly and strongly impact passenger satisfaction negatively. This demonstrates that the reliability of flight operations is the most critical factor in determining customer experience. The 'Fares' category came second. Interestingly, although 'Refunds' appear to be much more common in terms of the total number of complaints, experts have assessed that complaints related to pricing are more strategic and affect brand loyalty. A lack of transparency in ticket pricing policies or variable pricing practices, in particular, can lead to a loss of consumer trust.

The 'Baggage' category ranks third. The quantity of baggage complaints has been high and experts have assessed them as an important factor that directly affects service quality. Baggage problems are a frequent occurrence, especially on transfer flights, and are a key factor in reducing passenger satisfaction on connecting flights. The 'Reservations, Ticketing and Boarding' category was ranked fourth. This indicates that disruptions to ticketing and reservation systems can seriously affect the customer experience, particularly in the digital age.

The fifth category is 'Refunds'. Although this category has the highest percentage of complaints, experts rate its importance relatively low, perhaps reflecting their confidence that this problem can be more easily resolved over time with systemic solutions. Nevertheless, 'Refunds' remains a significant complaint category. Categories such as 'Other' and 'Animals' are at the bottom of the list and are considered by experts to be minor complaint types that do not significantly affect overall service quality or customer loyalty.

Another striking finding is that complaints relating to 'disability' and 'discrimination' are ranked low in terms of both complaint rates and expert assessments. This situation can be interpreted in two ways: either systematic progress has been made in these areas, or these issues are less visible but still need to be addressed. Therefore, it is recommended that these topics be given more attention, not based on their absolute numbers, but as issues requiring sensitivity.

5. Conclusion and Suggestions

This study found that the types and intensity of passenger complaints vary significantly among global airline alliances. A significant proportion of complaints relate to refunds, baggage services and reservation processes. Passengers experienced more issues related to refunds across all alliances, followed by problems with baggage and flights, and then reservations, ticketing, and pricing. In the expert assessment, the complaint category deemed most urgent was 'Flight Issues'. This was followed by the 'Fares' category, then baggage. In this context, the responses from passenger evaluations and expert opinions are consistent.

The negative impact of delays in airline operations on customer satisfaction is a well-discussed topic in the literature. In particular, operational issues such as flight disruptions, adverse weather conditions and unscheduled maintenance can have a direct impact on service quality (Arikan et al., 2016). The negative relationship between airport capacity and delays is also an important factor that contributes to customer dissatisfaction. Capacity shortages lead to operational difficulties, customer dissatisfaction and losses in market share for airlines (Gurtner et al., 2018: 2). Monmousseau et al. (2019) emphasise that, when it comes to predicting and analysing air traffic delays, passenger-centric data sources, particularly Twitter, can provide more information and enable more accurate predictions than flight-centric data.

In addition, uncertainty over delay times causes stress among passengers, which can lead to negative feelings towards the service provider. Therefore, airlines must inform passengers about flight delays in a realistic and careful manner. This is because delay information plays an important role in passengers' emotions and satisfaction with the airline (Au & Tse, 2019: 297). As delays can be caused by many factors, such as weather conditions, traffic congestion, equipment malfunctions and operational policies, a multi-dimensional solution is necessary (Mueller and Chatterji, 2002: 2; Sun et al., 2020: 1485).

Notably, longer flights are less likely to be cancelled (Xiong & Hansen, 2013: 69), and total delay costs can reach \$60 billion annually (Wen et al., 2020). This is an important warning for the industry. Furthermore, it has been observed that passenger rights regulations mitigate the impact of delays (Wang et al., 2020).

Overbooking is another long-standing issue in the airline industry. It is one of the main problems affecting passenger satisfaction, and various approaches have been tried to address it. Important aspects of industry regulations include penalising policies for no-show passengers and the obligation to compensate those who are denied boarding due to overbooking (Rothstein, 1971: 97; Sherman, 1979: 775).

Studies on baggage services have shown that lost, delayed or damaged luggage can cause serious financial and emotional distress for both passengers and airlines. Common problems include operational errors such as misdirection during transfers, loading errors and labelling errors. Notably, there have been allegations that airlines intentionally remove passenger baggage to carry more cargo (Franks, 2007: 737).

It has been determined that important areas for improvement in airline services for passengers with disabilities still exist. In particular, the loss of assistive devices such as wheelchairs, deficiencies in staff training, and issues with service quality create serious travel difficulties for disabled individuals (Major &

Hubbard, 2019: 50). Both internal procedures and accessible services supported by legal regulations are of great importance (Wood, 2022: 51).

In recent years, pet transportation has also become an important indicator of customer satisfaction in the airline industry. The increase in the number of pet owners, in particular, has made it necessary for airlines to review their service standards for this special customer group. Studies have shown that pet owners prioritise their pets' well-being during travel (Barnard-Nguyen et al., 2016; Brkljačić et al., 2020). The positive impact of travelling with pets on human happiness and quality of life is scientifically proven, with around 2 million pets travelling on commercial flights each year in the United States (Jahn et al., 2023). Designing pet transport processes that are safe, stress-free and transparent is therefore a strategic area that will increase customer satisfaction.

Another sensitive issue is complaints of discrimination. Following 9/11, South Asian, Arab and Muslim passengers in particular were subjected to racial profiling and discrimination, a serious human rights issue that is still being debated. The distinction between analysing passenger data for security purposes and discrimination remains a subject of academic and legal debate (Chandrasekhar, 2003: 241).

In theory, this study contributes to existing literature by demonstrating the applicability of multi-criteria decision-making methods in evaluating the quality of airline services. It also highlights the importance of expert opinions being supported by quantitative data and drawing attention to service areas with strategic effects on passenger satisfaction.

This study has several limitations. Firstly, the data set is limited to DOT reports. It is recommended that future studies conduct similar analyses with larger samples covering different continents. Furthermore, investigating the long-term effects of customer complaints on brand loyalty and airline preferences is suggested.

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